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ABSTRACT BOOK

Benthic communities on short-lived carbonate shoals (SLCS) versus Bahamian-type platforms on the Caribbean Large Igneous Province (CLIP)

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Middle-Upper Eocene SLCS established on the CLIP, now at bathyal depths, were dredged and drilled on the Beata Ridge (Fox et al. 1970) and dredged along the Hess Escarpment and on the Lower Nicaragua Rise (Baumgartner & Baumgartner-Mora, in Werner et al. 2010). These short-lived shallow-water deposits generally rest on Upper Cretaceous deep-water pelagic sediments or directly on the CLIP basement. They are, in turn overlain by pelagic deposits of Oligocene to Neogene age. Shallow-water benthic communities including lithothamnids, larger benthic Foraminifera (LBF) and corals colonized ephemeral guyot-type shoals of volcanic basement origin, that later drowned due to rapid thermal subsidence.

The discovery of these Eocene shallow water reefal sediments encroaching on basaltic CLIP-basement exposed on structural highs along the Hess Escarpment are fundamental for the understanding of the tectonic and magmatic history of the Hess Rise. The sediment facies and ages imply that the basement of the lower Hess rise originated at bathyal depths prior to the Campanian, became uplifted to sea level in Eocene times and reached again pelagic depths at latest in the middle Miocene.

The short lifetime of SLCS does usually not allow for the development of a typical carbonate platform morphology with ramps or crests and lagoons. When clear water conditions prevailed, any hard substrate (igneous basement or previously emerged and lithified sediments) were rapidly colonized in medium to high energy conditions by encrusting or attached photosynthetic organisms, here listed by their importance: 1. geniculate and encrusting coralline algae, 2. hyaline LBF, 3. corals. Large porcelaneous foraminifera are absent.

In contrast, the today emerged portion of the Beata Ridge is covered by a long-lived, well differentiated Bahamian-type carbonate platform that crops out in the south of Hispaniola, the Bahoruco Peninsula (Dominican Republic) and in the adjacent Massif de la Selle (Haiti). According to the Geothematic Mapping Project of the Dominican Republic, the first platform carbonates are of middle Eocene age. Based on our observations, the first shallow-water carbonates encroach on latest Cretaceous basalts, tuffs and conglomerates and contain *Ranikothalia catenula bermudezi* and *Neodiscocyclina barkeri*, both ranging not younger than Late Paleocene (Baumgartner-Mora & Baumgartner, 2017). The platform is continuous with a minor hiatus at the Eocene/Oligocene boundary (eustatic low-stand) and emerged around the Miocene/Pliocene boundary. *In situ* shallow water facies are limited to a relatively small area in the centre of the Bahoruco Peninsula. Thin-bedded peri-platform, sometimes cherty micrites, containing occasional platform-derived turbidites cover much of the area. They represent accumulation on a vast carbonate ramp that reached from shallow offshore to open marine pelagic conditions. Calciturbidites allow to study a synopsis of penecontemporaneously displaced and reworked bioclasts, derived from the platform interior.

The presence of large porcelaneous LBF, such as *Quasiborelis* and *Fabularia* clearly show the presence of an internal calm-water lagoon, populated by green and red algae, the main carbonate producers and LBF adapted to high light and clear-water low nutrient levels. Lack of accommodation space, particularly during eustatic lowstands, caused suspension of excess carbonate ooze and its transport into offshore ramp and slope areas. Occasional bioclastic turbidites may be generated by storm events on the shallow platform(s).

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